

Key Outcomes from ENERGATE Workshop in Turin

ESCOs as solution providers for incentive schemes

- Providing financial and technical support tailored to the needs of customers through Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs).
- Providing flexible solutions that advance sustainability goals and encourage data-driven decision-making for energy efficiency and environmental impact.
- Italy's Superbonus revision limits ESCo incentives, but ESCos remain key players in energy savings & sustainability.

Need for ESCos consolidation & investment in energy efficiency

Fragmented market:

The ESCo sector is fragmented and struggles to attract large-scale investors. Consolidation could help appeal to them.

Market challenges:

SMEs & ESCos face financing barriers, as banks hesitate to fund non-standardised energy projects.

Scaling for finance and collaboration:

By joining forces with other companies, the sector could increase market presence and raise more capital.

Aligning regulations:

Better EU-national regulation alignment needed to empower ESCos & reduce inefficiencies.

ENERGATE driving sustainable investments

- Optimised project selection - Standardised criteria, simplifying selection based on returns, technology, and timing.
- Strong ESCo & asset owners partnerships for tailored energy efficiency solutions across regions.
- Scalability & multi-country alignment – Supports expansion across Europe with attractive investment pipeline.

Sustainability & energy efficiency in the face of global population growth

- Population growth and urban demand cause increasing pressure on resources, housing, and infrastructure.
- Over 2 billion people currently live in inadequate living conditions, underscoring the need for sustainable solutions.
- Innovative approach to address the above issues: Focus on integrating sustainability across four pillars: Energy & Ecosystem Resources, Built Environment, Technology, Social Innovation.
- EPBD compliance remains a challenge, especially in Italy—long-term investments in future technologies are essential.
- CO₂-focused incentives & standardised criteria are crucial for sustainable energy progress.

How the ENERGATE Platform ensures flexibility to accommodate the unique needs of its users

- Benchmarking functionality unlocks strategic insights & informed decisions.
- Flexible, modular services with potential for enhanced usability through vertical and geographic features.
- Regional filters for better matchmaking, especially in countries with diverse regulations and market conditions.
- Keyword-based search can improve project selection and connectivity.
- Connecting stakeholders, bridging market fragmentation, creating opportunities for scaling and driving impactful change.

